

Variation of leaf blast lesion, IRRI, 1988. See table for the description of each lesion type. The bar indicates 1 cm.

coalesce to cause considerable leaf damage.

Type 9 lesions are frequently observed on highly susceptible varieties at the early seedling stage; plants with this lesion type either die quickly or become

severely stunted. In the field, disease progress on cultivars with lesion types 5, 7, or 9 vary greatly, depending on the level of quantitative resistance and environmental conditions at different growth stages.

Classification code for leaf BI lesion type. IRRI, 1988.

Code	Description
0	No lesions
1	Small brown specks of pinpoint size or larger brown specks without sporulating center
3	Small, roundish to slightly elongated necrotic sporulating spots, about 1-2 mm in diameter with a distinct brown margin or yellow halo
5	Narrow or slightly elliptical lesions, 1-2 mm in breadth, more than 3 mm long with a brown margin.
7	Broad spindle-shaped lesion with yellow, brown, or purple margin
9	Rapidly coalescing small, whitish, grayish, or bluish lesions without distinct margins

In field assessment of varietal resistance, predominant lesion type and disease severity (i.e., leaf area affected) should be recorded separately, to indicate qualitative as well as quantitative resistance at different growth stages. When an entry has mixed lesion types, the lesion with higher code number should be recorded. □

Insect resistance

Donors for resistance to Andhra Pradesh biotype 4 gall midge (GM)

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An unprecedented shift in the population of GM *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) prevalent in Srikakulam and Vizainagaram districts has occurred since 1986. Almost all varieties—including Phalguna and Surekha—known for their resistance in these districts, were severely damaged. The loss in about 31,000 ha was estimated to be more than \$410 million.

We reared the GM population from this area on Phalguna plants under strict quarantine in the greenhouse during 1987, and evaluated 90 GM donors with

resistance to the Hyderabad population (biotype 1) against the Srikakulam population under artificial infestation.

Only 12 donors showed resistance to the new population (see table). All traditional resistance donors, like Eswarakora (resistant to biotypes 1 and 3), Siam 29 and Leuang 152 (resistant to biotypes 1 and 2), were susceptible. In addition, improved varieties Phalguna and Surekha (IR8/Siam 29), Kakatiya (TR8/W1263), Rajendradhan 202 (IR8/W1251), Samridhi (R68-I/Jaya), Asha and Usha (IR22/W12631) were susceptible. All 90 donors maintained their resistance against the Hyderabad population.

GM donors showing resistance to biotype 4 population of Srikakulam in the greenhouse. Andhra Pradesh, India.

CR-MR 1523	T10	Ptb 18
Velluthacheera	T1425	Ptb 21
Vellachenipan	T1432	Aganni
NHTA8	T1477	Banglei

Evidently the Srikakulam population is different from the three known biotypes in the country and is more virulent. Hence, it may be considered biotype 4. Some advanced cultures involving donors like Velluthacheera are being tested for their yield potential and adaptability in Srikakulam. □

Short-duration donors for brown planthopper (BPH) resistance

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We screened 200 traditional cultivars of Madhya Pradesh in Hyderabad in 1987 for resistance to BPH. The standard seedbox screening technique had two replications.